

Section 1: Applicants

Name of the main applicant	Dr. Egon Willighagen
Affiliation – institution	Maastricht University
Affiliation – department	Dept of Translational Genomics
Position	universitair docent
End date of contract	
Guarantee needed & added yes/no/n.a.	
E-mail address	egon.willighagen@maastrichtuniversity.nl
ORCID ID	https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7542-0286

Name of the co-applicant	Dr. Tooba Abbassi-Daloi
Affiliation – institution	Maastricht University
Affiliation – department	Dept of Translational Genomics
Position	Senior Researcher
End date of contract	
Guarantee added yes/no/n.a.	
E-mail address	
ORCID ID	https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4904-3269

Name of the co-applicant	Dr. Anna Niehues
Affiliation – institution	Leiden University Medical Center (LUMC)
Affiliation – department	Advanced Data Management, Department of Biomedical Data Sciences
Position	Senior Data Steward
End date of contract	
Guarantee added yes/no/n.a.	
E-mail address	
ORCID ID	https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9839-5439

Name of the co-applicant	Dr. Magnus Palmblad
Affiliation – institution	Leiden University Medical Center
Affiliation – department	Center for Proteomics and Metabolomics
Position	Associate Professor, Bioinformatics Group Leader
End date of contract	
Guarantee added yes/no/n.a.	
E-mail address	
ORCID ID	https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5865-8994

Open Science Infrastructure 2024 full proposal - Small

Name of the co-applicant	Dr. Leon Mei
Affiliation – institution	Leiden University Medical Center
Affiliation – department	Sequencing Analysis Support Core
Position	Head
End date of contract	
Guarantee added yes/no/n.a.	
E-mail address	
ORCID ID	https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1781-5508

Name of the co-applicant	Dr. Eleni Mina
Affiliation – institution	Leiden University Medical Center
Affiliation – department	Human Genetics
Position	Senior Researcher
End date of contract	
Guarantee added yes/no/n.a.	
E-mail address	
ORCID ID	https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8972-9206

Name of the co-applicant	Dr. Friederike Ehrhart
Affiliation – institution	Maastricht University
Affiliation – department	Department of Translational Genomics
Position	Assistant Professor / universitair docent
End date of contract	
Guarantee added yes/no/n.a.	
E-mail address	
ORCID ID	https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7770-620X

Name of the co-applicant	Dr. Danyel Jennen
Affiliation – institution	Maastricht University
Affiliation – department	Department of Translational Genomics
Position	Associate Professor
End date of contract	
Guarantee added yes/no/n.a.	
E-mail address	
ORCID ID	https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8618-2487

Section 2: Summary

Proposed project title	Schema-Driven Interoperability of Biomedical Data Resources for Improved Knowledge Dissemination and Reuse
Project duration (in months)	24

English public summary

Biomedical data is scattered across diverse databases, each with a different scope and design, making integration and analysis challenging. This project creates an open, interoperable framework to connect these databases, enabling efficient access and data use. By applying schema harmonization, aligning database designs, and using open science approaches, it promotes data transparency, reusability, and interoperability. Our approach implements the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) principles, ensuring analysis across databases is accurate and transparent, e.g., when combining gene expression data with gene variant knowledge. The resulting access to the integrated databases simplifies data exploration and maximizes the scientific insights.

Word count EN-SUM (max 100): 99

Dutch public summary

Biomedische data is verstopt in uiteenlopende databases, elk met een eigen ontwerp en toepassing. Hierdoor is combineren een uitdaging. Dit project maakt een vrij-beschikbare infrastructuur die deze databases met elkaar verbindt, waardoor efficiënte toegang en analyse van data mogelijk wordt. Door databaseontwerpen aan elkaar te koppelen en open wetenschap te gebruiken, bevordert het de herbruikbaarheid en interoperabiliteit van kennis. Onze aanpak implementeert de FAIR-principes (vindbaar, toegankelijk, interoperabel, en herbruikbaar) en garandeert accuraat en transparant data-analyse, zoals voor het combineren van genexpressiegegevens met kennis over genvarianten. Toegang tot de gecombineerde databases vereenvoudigt gegevensverkenning en maximaliseert de wetenschappelijke inzichten.

Word count NL-SUM (max 100): 97

Section 3: Alignment with the scope of the call

3.1 Vision for the project and alignment with the aim of this call

This project aims to unify fragmented biomedical databases by developing a smooth, transparent and reproducible integration. It will improve interoperability between databases, aligning with the call's objective to support open science by investing in digital infrastructures. This project complements ELIXIR-NL's efforts within the ELIXIR Tools and Interoperability Platforms by closing gaps and improving interoperability. We will combine schema analysis and open-source tools to promote interoperability and community engagement, key principles of open science.

This infrastructure provides a foundation for all stakeholders, including academic researchers and industry partners, enabling more effective access to high-quality databases. By ensuring data is discoverable, interoperable and reusable, we can foster innovative research, drive collaborative projects and accelerate scientific discovery. Furthermore, the project addresses the funder's priority for long-term sustainability by using open protocols, encouraging community engagement and ensuring the infrastructure remains adaptable to future needs.

Word count (max. 150): 140

3.2 User communities, challenges and needs

Life science data spans diverse biomedical databases with different formats, ontologies and schemas, making integration challenging. This emphasizes the need for infrastructure that facilitates knowledge sharing and helps researchers define data semantics, improving reuse and reproducibility. Structured schema information aids integration and promotes data sharing and interoperability.

This initiative will prioritize databases from the European Research Alliance for Rare Diseases (ERDERA) and the ELIXIR Rare Disease (RD) and Proteomics Communities, where improved interoperability offers high impact. For RD, this enhances access to scattered data, supporting faster diagnosis and treatment development. For Proteomics, it enables linking protein data with biomedical information—gene expression, molecular interactions, gene-disease associations and metabolic data.

Metadata on access methods and database structures will be enriched to improve discoverability and usability in workflows. Bio.tools, covering over 2600 portals, will include descriptions of access methods (like “SPARQL endpoint”) and supported query languages. Galaxy-NL will adopt harmonized schemas into FAIR workflows and support integration with external databases. BioDataFuse will use these schemas to streamline the integration of diverse databases into domain-specific knowledge graphs. Connecting schema harmonization with flexible tools keeps infrastructure adaptable and accessible to researchers, data analysts and developers, reinforcing the open science ecosystem.

Word count (max. 200): 196

3.3 Alignment of project with OS principles

This proposal aligns with the principles of open science, particularly through the harmonization of data schemas in open-access biomedical databases, prioritizing those recommended by ELIXIR Europe. The infrastructure will operate under a transparent governance model aligned with UNESCO's open science recommendations, guaranteeing decision-making remains community-driven.

By ensuring schemas follow FAIR principles, researchers will be able to share, discover and integrate data effectively, making integration easier and faster, enhancing the efficiency of biomedical research. Our efforts to harmonize and enhance metadata across platforms like bio.tools and Galaxy improve the visibility and accessibility of biomedical data, supporting the broader open science ecosystem.

The project will contribute to open science by promoting tools and workflows that are openly accessible and reusable. Workflow templates, tutorials and harmonized schema resources will be shared through platforms like UseGalaxy.eu and WorkflowHub, and indexed on platforms such as ELIXIR TeSS and SURF's Taxila.nl. These resources empower researchers to implement FAIR workflows, improving data interoperability and the reproducibility of results across diverse research domains.

By integrating with community-driven platforms and ensuring schema information is openly accessible, this initiative embodies open science principles, promoting transparency, interoperability and community-driven governance.

Word count (max. 200): 189

Section 4: Feasibility

4.1 Project plan

The project will be executed in three work packages (WPs):

WP1. Schema Analysis of Prioritized Databases

In this WP, we will prioritize databases from ERDERA, ELIXIR RD and Proteomics Communities based on certain characteristics such as resource size (e.g., number of records), user base, Open Science compliance, and maintenance and curation status. Specific examples from ERDERA include newer databases such as Treatabome and the PCOM/PROM database, as well as established databases used in the RD research, such as WikiPathways [1], Orphanet and DisGeNet.

Proteomics use cases will also be considered, where integration challenges are particularly evident. These typically start with mass spectrometry data and require linking to RNA/DNA sequence databases for protein identification, structural databases for contextualizing post-translational modifications, and protein-protein interaction databases to interpret quantitative correlations. However, this multi-step integration is often hindered by inconsistent data models, fragmented schema models and limited interoperability between resources.

To address these challenges and in line with the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) principles [2], we will map existing database schemas to established ontologies and standards, such as those from the Open Biological and Biomedical Ontology (OBO) Foundry [3], using services like [BridgeDb](#) [4], to ensure consistent ontological mappings. Where schemas are poorly defined or absent, we will apply schema inference techniques to derive structured representations from existing data to ensure interoperability even in the absence of formal documentation. This will be achieved using open-source tools like [VOID Generator](#), which generates statistical insights on a target database to help understand its underlying schema, and [sheXer](#) [5], which extracts Shape Expressions (ShEx) to define semantic relationships.

This analysis will generate standardized ShEx and RDF metadata [6], which will be used to annotate these databases with enriched semantic information. The outputs of WP1 will establish a standardized foundation for subsequent interoperability efforts, supporting a connected and accessible ecosystem for biomedical data.

WP2. Schema Documentation and Integration

In WP2, the database schema insights from WP1 will be consumed by bio.tools, including to enrich its annotations of database portals, which will be prioritized based on usage (citations, mentions) and uniqueness (i.e., not containing information already available from other databases). We will use Bioschemas [7] and EDAM ontology [8, 9] as standards to ensure that all schema information is accessible and structured to support the FAIR data ecosystem. In addition, the schema information will be systematically incorporated into the BioDataFuse knowledge graph [10] to enable smoother data integration across different research domains. Integrating this infrastructure with existing services and platforms will increase its utility and prevent fragmentation and duplication [11,12]. This WP will then implement several domain-specific workflows made possible through the schema analyses and annotations. Whenever feasible, the workflows will be implemented in Galaxy in collaboration with WP3.

WP3. Galaxy Workflow Integration

WP3 focuses on integrating harmonized schemas into Galaxy [13], a world-renowned data analysis workflow platform across multiple scientific domains, as well as other FAIR workflow systems. Based on identified use cases, resources and workflows will be developed and incorporated into the Galaxy ToolShed. The bio.tools descriptions of database interfaces and their mappings in the KG will guide the integration of these data sources, enhancing interoperability and usability within Galaxy [14].

By aligning these workflows with identified schemas, we aim to improve the usability of databases in Galaxy and potentially other FAIR workflows, like Nextflow, CWL and WDL, facilitating the integration of external databases into new or existing workflows. Domain ontology-based mapping tools will be developed to support such workflow harmonization tasks, similar to [Janis](#), and recent annotation of Bioconductor packages [9].

Through the collaboration with the Galaxy-NL community, we will link this WP with the national infrastructure initiative at SURF and education activities at hogeschools and universities to support user groups lacking local infrastructure resources and technical expertise. Therefore, we can ensure a stable developer and user community to sustain the WP deliverables further.

To support adoption, training materials and workflow templates will be published via the Galaxy Training Network, UseGalaxy.eu, WorkflowHub, ELIXIR TeSS, and SURF's Taxila.nl. These resources will help researchers use and visualize the integrated data.

Throughout all WPs, we will ensure close collaboration with ELIXIR and other community platforms to ensure the project follows best practices for sustainability, openness, and alignment with the needs of the research community.

Word count SEC41 (max. 750): 707

4.2 Team composition

Name, surname	Affiliation	Expertise	Role/contributions
Dr. E.L. (Egon) Willighagen	UM	Cheminformatics, ontology development, workflow node development	Project manager, WP advisor, representation in: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ INOSC and ELIXIR Europe ■ BridgeDb Project Taxila.nl
Dr. T. (Tooba) Abbassi-Daloi	UM	Bioinformatics, data integration, FAIR, knowledge representation, schema analysis, BioDataFuse, WikiPathways	WP1 and WP2 co-leader, WP3 advisor <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Define use cases, prioritize and evaluate databases ■ Lead schema analysis and integration ■ Coordinate outreach to collaborators Represent the project in the ELIXIR Interoperability Platform
Dr. A. (Anna) Niehues	LUMC	Bioinformatics, FAIR data stewardship, research software, FAIR implementation	WP1 and WP2 advisor (Liaison to LUMC DCC & Health-RI) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Support metadata standards (e.g., HealthDCAT-AP) ■ Align with national software stewardship initiatives ■ Facilitate the adoption of project resources within LUMC DCC FAIRification of research outputs
Dr. M. (Magnus) Palmblad	LUMC	Bioinformatics, proteomics, ontologies, AI, ELIXIR Tools Platform	WP2 co-leader, WP3 advisor <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Supervise database annotation in bio.tools ■ Supervise proteomics use cases Liaise with EDAM and bio.tools developers.
Dr. L. (Leon) Mei	LUMC	Bioinformatics, NGS pipelines (Galaxy, WDL/Cromwell, Nextflow, Snakemake), Galaxy-NL	WP3 co-leader <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Supervise FAIR data analysis workflow development Liaise with the Galaxy community on schema dissemination and integrate workflow frameworks
Dr. E. (Eleni) Mina	LUMC	Bioinformatics, RD research, data integration, ERDERA, ELIXIR RD	WP1, WP2 advisor <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Define RD use cases ■ Evaluate outcomes for RD relevance Advice on schema alignment
Dr. F. (Friederike) Ehrhart	UM	Bioinformatics, RD research, ERDERA, ELIXIR RD, WikiPathways	WP1 co-leader, WP2 advisor <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Provide concrete use cases from RD communities in ERDERA, ELIXIR ■ Advice on research questions and database selection Support outcome evaluation and publication
Dr. D. (Danyel) Jennen	UM	Bioinformatics, data protection, FAIR stewardship, FAIR implementation	WP3 co-leader, WP2 advisor <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Support schema integration into Galaxy workflows Advice on metadata schemas and their integration
To be hired	UM	FAIR data stewardship	Contribute to schema analysis (WP1), support integration in BioDataFuse (WP2), assist documentation and dissemination of schemas and workflows (WP3).

To be hired	LUMC	Bioinformatics, computational proteomics, workflows	Annotate portals in bio.tools (WP2), implement and demonstrate proteomics use cases using portals and schema analysis from WP1 in Galaxy (WP3).
-------------	------	---	---

Word count (max. 350): 343

4.3 Risk management

Risk	Likelihood and impact	Risk mitigation strategy
Changes to the schema of databases	Likelihood: low (changes) to medium (additions) Impact: high	Regular communication with database providers to stay updated on schema changes. Implement version control for schema updates.
Limited access to databases for schema understanding	Likelihood: medium Impact: high	Contacting the database providers and negotiating access agreements in advance. Exploring public databases and open data alternatives.
Inconsistent or missing metadata	Likelihood: high Impact: medium	Use schema inference tools (e.g., VoID Generator, sheXer) to derive metadata and ensure consistency across databases. Collaborate with data curators for improvements.
Technical challenges during workflow integration	Likelihood: medium Impact: medium	Involve technical experts early in the integration process. Provide detailed documentation for smooth implementation.
Change in the license terms of databases	Likelihood: medium Impact: high	Review database licenses at project start and regularly monitor for updates. Prefer open-licensed resources when possible.

Word count (max. 150): 147

4.4 Budget

Position	HOT scale	Institu- tion	Total FTE	Years active	Amount
Research Software Engineer	HOT 2.1 - 10	LUMC	0.78	2	€ 68,698.50
FAIR Data Steward	HOT 2.1 - 10	UM	1.92	2	€ 169,104.00

Material/IT Type	Description	Cost calculation	Total (€)
Other	Project team and stakeholder F2F meetings	Catering for 4 meetings with 20 attendees	€ 4,000.00
Other	Travel costs to attend project meetings	4 travel costs for 20 persons	€ 2,800.00
(international) travel and accommodation expenses incl. conference visit	e.g. Attendance of data steward and reserach software engineer to BioSB Conference, Galaxy Community Conference and BioHackathon Europe, every year 2026-2027	1,000 per person per year	€ 4,000.00

Total Personnel requested: 237,802.50

Total Material/IT requested: 10.800,00

Total budget requested: 248,602.50

4.5 Budget justification

The budget primarily supports two key roles essential for delivering project outputs: a FAIR Data Steward (0.75 FTE at UM) and a Research Software Engineer (RSE, 0.3 FTE at LUMC). The RSE will develop workflows, integrate schema information into bio.tools and Galaxy, and implement use cases from WP2 and WP3. The FAIR Data Steward will lead schema harmonization and documentation, contribute to metadata enrichment, and support integration with BioDataFuse (WP1-WP3). Their efforts are critical to ensuring technical implementation and alignment with FAIR and open science principles.

We allocate €4,000 for catering and logistics for four face-to-face meetings, each involving 20 participants. These sessions are vital for hands-on collaboration and aligning activities.

Travel costs (€2,800) cover travel costs to project meetings to support in-person coordination across LUMC and UM teams. An additional €4,000 is budgeted for travel and conference participation (e.g., BioSB, Galaxy Community Conference and BioHackathon Europe), allowing the RSE and data steward to engage with international communities, present results, and align with broader initiatives such as ELIXIR.

The budget is lean, cost-effective, and directly supports core deliverables while ensuring meaningful collaboration and sustainable impact.

Word count (max. 200): 186

4.6 Impact plan

This project will significantly impact the RD community by addressing the fragmentation of biomedical data. RD research is often hindered by limited, siloed datasets. By harmonizing schema structures and integrating multiple RD-associated databases within an ontology-driven framework, the project will enable standardized annotations, enhanced cross-referencing, and streamlined data exchange. This will accelerate the discovery of candidate therapies and improve diagnostic accuracy, particularly for currently misdiagnosed or undiagnosed RDs.

In the proteomics domain, the integration of mass spectrometry data with genomic, structural, and molecular interaction databases will support more comprehensive and biologically meaningful analyses. Researchers will be able to extract insights more efficiently and draw more precise and actionable biological conclusions.

The framework developed for schema extraction and harmonization will improve data integration and downstream analyses and will be reusable for other domains, including broader health and clinical research settings. This promotes long-term scalability and transferability of the infrastructure.

To reach this impact, we will publish schema templates, workflows, and documentation via platforms like WorkflowHub and UseGalaxy.eu. We will engage with stakeholders through training and national infrastructures (e.g., LUMC DCC, SURF, ELIXIR-NL), ensuring adoption, feedback, and long-term sustainability.

Word count (max. 200): 189

Section 5: Sustainability and software management

Section 5.1: Sustainability plan

This project focuses on the development of scripts for schema inference, schema usage demonstrations, integration and Galaxy workflows, rather than on the delivery of long-term maintained software. These lightweight, purpose-built scripts will be openly shared to support transparency, reproducibility, and reuse.

All scripts, workflows, and schema-related materials will be made available through public repositories on GitHub under an Apache License 2.0. While they are not designed for ongoing maintenance, their availability, combined with clear documentation, will allow other researchers and developers to adapt and reuse them as needed.

To ensure long-term accessibility, we will archive releases on Zenodo and SoftwareHeritage with appropriate metadata and persistent identifiers (DOIs). This approach safeguards the outputs for future reference and reuse, even beyond the project duration.

Sustainability will be further supported by integrating schema outputs and documentation into community platforms such as bio.tools, Galaxy, and BioDataFuse, where they can be directly used and maintained as part of those ecosystems. By aligning with established standards like EDAM ontology and Bioschemas, schema resources will remain relevant and adaptable as the broader FAIR data infrastructure evolves.

Word count (max 300): 179

Section 5.2: Software management plan

1. Please provide a brief description of your software, stating its purpose and intended audience.

The project does not produce standalone software, but it can include scripts for schema inference, scripts for demonstrating example usage of the created schemas, and example Galaxy workflows utilizing these schemas. The intended audience for these scripts is researchers, bioinformaticians, and data scientists working in life sciences.

2. How will you manage versioning of your software?

We will use GitHub to support version control with Git. This will allow us to track changes, manage different versions, and maintain transparency throughout the development lifecycle.

3. How will you make your software publicly available? What licence will your software have?

The scripts will be openly published on GitHub under a permissive open-source license (Apache License 2.0). Releases will be archived on Zenodo and SoftwareHeritage upon publishing the schemas to ensure proper citation and long-term accessibility.

4. How will users of your software be able to cite your software?

A CITATION.cff file will be included in the GitHub repository, providing users with the necessary citation details for referencing the software.

5. How will your software be documented? Please describe your plans for: user documentation, documentation for future developers and for installation requirements. Please provide links to documentation if already available.

User Documentation: Clear guides on how to use the scripts and workflows.

Developer Documentation: An overview of the code structure, design, and usage examples for future developers. This will include in-line comments in the code to explain the logic.

Installation Requirements: Dependencies (e.g., libraries, tools) will be specified, and setup instructions will be provided to ensure smooth installation for end-users.

6. How will contribution guidelines and governance structure of your software be documented?

Contribution guidelines and the governance structure will be clearly documented in the GitHub repository. This will outline how external contributors can submit issues, pull requests, and follow best practices for contributing to the scripts.

7. How will your software be tested?

Testing will primarily focus on ensuring that the scripts correctly perform the intended schema development and usage tasks. Given that the scripts are designed to document the process rather than to be long-term tools, the testing will involve ensuring that each script works as expected within the scope of the project.

8. How will you check that it respects the licences of libraries and dependencies it uses?

We will perform a review of the libraries and dependencies used in the project to ensure compliance with the licenses. Since this project is focused on developing scripts for schema documentation and use, we will ensure that any external dependencies are either open source with permissive licenses (such as Apache 2.0 or MIT) or are appropriately licensed for inclusion in the repository. This review will be conducted at the start of the project and revisited before any public release, particularly for any changes or additions made during the project's lifespan.

9. How will your software be packaged and distributed?

As the project does not produce standalone software, there will be no formal packaging. Instead, scripts and Galaxy workflow examples will be distributed via GitHub repositories with clear folder structures, descriptive filenames, and README.md files. Galaxy workflows will also be shared through WorkflowHub and UseGalaxy.eu where applicable.

10. What level of support will be provided for users of the software and how will this support be organised?

No formal user support is planned, as the scripts are illustrative and not intended for production use. However, we will provide sufficient documentation, including example inputs and outputs, to allow other researchers to understand and adapt them. During the project period, issues can be raised through GitHub, where the project team will address them on a best-effort basis.

11. How do you plan to ensure long term maintenance of your software?

Not applicable. The scripts developed in this project document the schema development process and are not intended for long-term maintenance. However, they will be publicly available on GitHub, with clear documentation, allowing the community to maintain or adapt them if needed.

Section 6: References

1. Martens, M., Ammar, A., Riutta, A., Waagmeester, A., Slenter, D. N., Hanspers, K., A. Miller, R., Digles, D., Lopes, E. N., Ehrhart, F., Dupuis, L. J., Winckers, L. A., Coort, S. L., Willighagen, E. L., Evelo, C. T., Pico, A. R., & Kutmon, M. (2021). WikiPathways: Connecting communities. *Nucleic Acids Research*, 49(D1), D613–D621. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkaa1024>
2. Jacobsen, A., de Miranda Azevedo, R., Juty, N., Batista, D., Coles, S., Cornet, R., Courtot, M., Crosas, M., Dumontier, M., Evelo, C. T., Goble, C., Guizzardi, G., Hansen, K. K., Hasnain, A., Hettne, K., Heringa, J., Hooft, R. W. W., Imming, M., Jeffery, K. G., ... Schultes, E. (2020). FAIR Principles: Interpretations and Implementation Considerations. *Data Intelligence*, 2(1–2), 10–29. https://doi.org/10.1162/dint_r_00024
3. Jackson, R., Matentzoglou, N., Overton, J.A., Vita, R., Balhoff, J.P., Buttigieg, P.L., Carbon, S., Courtot, M., Diehl, A.D., Dooley, D.M., Duncan, W.D., Harris, N.L., Haendel, M.A., Lewis, S.E., Natale, D.A., Osumi-Sutherland, D., Ruttner, A., Schriml, L.M., Smith, B., Stoeckert, C.J. Jr., Vasilevsky, N.A., Walls, R.L., Zheng, J., & Mungall, C.J. (2021). OBO Foundry in 2021: Operationalizing open data principles to evaluate ontologies. *Database*, 2021, baab069. <https://doi.org/10.1093/database/baab069>
4. van Iersel, M.P., Pico, A.R., Kelder, T., Gao, J., Ho, I., Hanspers, K., Conklin, B.R., & Evelo, C.T. (2010). The BridgeDb framework: Standardized access to gene, protein and metabolite identifier mapping services. *BMC Bioinformatics*, 11(1), 5. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2105-11-5>
5. Fernández-Álvarez, D., Labra-Gayo, J.E., & Gayo-Avello, D. (2022). Automatic extraction of shapes using sheXer. *Knowledge-Based Systems*, 238, 107975. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.knsys.2021.107975>
6. Waagmeester, A., Willighagen, E. L., Su, A. I., Kutmon, M., Gayo, J. E. L., Fernández-Álvarez, D., Groom, Q., Schaap, P. J., Verhagen, L. M., & Koehorst, J. J. (2021). A protocol for adding knowledge to Wikidata: Aligning resources on human coronaviruses. *BMC Biology*, 19(1), 12. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12915-020-00940-y>
7. Gray, A.J.G., Goble, C.A., & Jimenez, R. (2017). Bioschemas: From Potato Salad to Protein Annotation. In *International Semantic Web Conference (Posters, Demos & Industry Tracks)*. <https://pure.manchester.ac.uk/ws/portalfiles/portal/221774536/paper579.pdf>
8. Black, M., Lamothe, L., Eldakoury, H., Kierkegaard, M., Priya, A., Machinda, A., Khanduja, U.S., Patoliya, D., Rath, R., Nico, T.P.C., Umutesi, G., Blankenburg, C., Op, A., Chieke, P., Babatunde, O., Laurie, S., Neumann, S., Schwämmle, V., Kuzmin, I., Hunter, C., Karr, J., Ison, J., Gaignard, A., Brancotte, B., Ménager, H., & Kalaš, M. (2022). EDAM: The bioscientific data analysis ontology (update 2021) [version 1; not peer reviewed]. *F1000Research*, 11(ISCB Comm J): 1. <https://doi.org/10.7490/f1000research.1118900.1>
9. Rioualen, C., Barre, A., Dartigues, B., Carey, V. J., Kalas, M., Lobentanzer, S., Menager, H., Neumann, S., Nishida, K., Schwämmle, V., Vu, A. N., Willighagen, E., & Doyle, M. A. (2025). BioHackEU24 report: Integrating Bioconductor packages with the ELIXIR Research Software Ecosystem using EDAM. *BioHackXiv*. https://doi.org/10.37044/osf.io/dsgnw_v1
10. Gadiya, Y., Ammar, A., Willighagen, E., Martinat, D., Claudia Sima, A., Balci, H., Abbassi-Daloui, T. (2023). BioHackEU23 report: Extending interoperability of experimental data using modular queries across biomedical resources. *BioHackXiv*. https://osf.io/preprints/biohackxiv/mhsgp_v1
11. Palmblad, M., Lamprecht, A-L., Ison, J., Schwämmle, V. (2019) Automated workflow composition in mass spectrometry-based proteomics. *Bioinformatics*, 35(4). <https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/bty646>
12. Lamprecht, A.-L., Palmblad, M., Ison, J., Schwämmle, V., Al Manir, M. S., Altintas, I., Baker, C. J. O., Ben Hadj Amor, A., Capella-Gutierrez, S., Charonyktakis, P., Crusoe, M. R., Gil, Y., Goble, C., Griffin, T. J., Groth, P., Ienasescu, H., Jagtap, P., Kalaš, M., Kasalica, V., ... Wolstencroft, K. (2021). Perspectives on automated composition of workflows in the life sciences. *F1000Research*, 10, 897. <https://doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.54159.1>
13. Lamothe, L., Jensen, J. R. B., Ienasescu, H., Gustafsson, O. J. R., Gaignard, A., Repchevsky, D., Svobodová, R., Raček, T., Antol, M., Palmblad, M., Kalaš, M., & Menager, H. (2023). An evaluation of EDAM coverage in the Tools Ecosystem and prototype integration of Galaxy and WorkflowHub systems. *BioHackXiv*. <https://doi.org/10.37044/osf.io/79kie>
14. Willighagen, E., & Mélius, J. (2017). Automatic OpenAPI to Bio.tools Conversion. *BioRxiv*. <https://doi.org/10.1101/170274>

Section 7: Declaration

By submitting this form, I declare that:

- I and all the individuals involved in this proposal satisfy the nationally and internationally accepted standards for scientific conduct as stated in the Netherlands [Code of Conduct for Research Integrity](#) (The Universities of the Netherlands).
- The research organisation has been informed of this grant application and the research organisation accepts the grant conditions of this programme.
- I have completed this application form truthfully.
- I have submitted a pre-proposal for this Call for proposals in ISAAC.